

Initial velocity distribution and consequent spatial distribution of fragments

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A qualitative understanding of what observed features are due to the dynamics and what are due to initial conditions was obtained in a paper we published in the JAS.

Our previous work

- ▶ We have discovered a way to do *Eulerian orbit dynamics*, propagating the spatial number density from a point fragmentation given an initial velocity distribution at that point.
- ▶ Conferences early 2016 to present, Journal of the Astronautical Sciences (online January 2019).
- ▶ This produces interesting plots

We would like a better understanding of three things

- ▶ The risk associated with a fragmentation, in general.
- ▶ The initial velocity distribution resulting from specific and general classes of events.
- ▶ The importance of this distribution and whether it can be inferred from the ensuing debris cloud.

The goal of the present investigation is to contribute to the last of these.

- ▶ **Inferability** is an indication of how well the initial velocity distribution can be determined from final spatial distribution.
- ▶ More specifically, propagate two different distributions over the same time interval, and find the disparity of the result.

Input disparity	Output disparity	Conclusion
High	Low	Low inferability
High	High	High inferability
Low	Low	Low inferability unless high/high
Low	High	Chaotic

- ▶ Try high disparity inputs and see how disparate the output is.
- ▶ The weakest form of inferability could be called **distinguishability**, in essence, are two densities from the same or different source distributions?

Implications of high inferability

- ▶ High inferability implies good forensics: determining the source distribution (and thus perhaps the cause) from the result.
- ▶ Is result “consistent with” hypothesized cause?
- ▶ Note: complete observations are assumed.
- ▶ Note: inferability is a time-dependent function.

Ways to compare distributions

- ▶ Some are measures of how similar distributions are, some are measures of how different they are.
- ▶ Unnormalized, not dimensionless means there is no maximum value to represent the opposite case (similar/different).
- ▶ Goal: symmetric, able to distinguish significant movement of density a small distance from the same amount a large distance.
- ▶ Ideally, “Earth mover distance” but that requires a complicated calculation on a structure we don’t know.
- ▶ Root mean square (RMS) will give large numbers for significant variation, but can’t show the amount of material “moved”.
- ▶ RMS is an easy calculation, chosen.

- ▶ How the fragments' velocity relative to the pre-fragmentation velocity is distributed.
- ▶ For each Lambert mode (route) that does not intersect the earth, the initial velocity is computed and then the density computed from the velocity distribution.
- ▶ Previously, we have assumed an isotropic velocity distribution (in Δv or inertial velocity) and described the magnitude with a scalar distribution functions.
- ▶ Anisotropic velocity vector distributions are best described in Cartesian coordinates.

Normal velocity distribution

$$f(\mathbf{v}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi^3 \det \Sigma}} e^{-\frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{v} - \boldsymbol{\mu})^T \Sigma^{-1}(\mathbf{v} - \boldsymbol{\mu})}$$

- ▶ The velocity change distribution from the fragmentation is presumed to be multivariate normal.
- ▶ Covariance matrix is assumed proportional to the 3×3 identity, $\Sigma = \sigma_v^2 I_{3 \times 3}$.
- ▶ A good approximation for the present purpose, though can't have infinite velocity.
- ▶ Anisotropy only from modal velocity vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$.
- ▶ Covariance is spherically symmetric, the only anisotropy due to the nonzero modal velocity change.

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Isotropy and anisotropy

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- Isotropy: if the mode is at the origin $\Delta \mathbf{v}_{\text{mode}} = \mathbf{0}$, the magnitude follows a Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution

$$p(\Delta \mathbf{v}; \sigma_v, \Delta \mathbf{v}_{\text{mode}})$$

$$\propto |\Delta \mathbf{v} - \Delta \mathbf{v}_{\text{mode}}|^2 e^{-|\Delta \mathbf{v} - \Delta \mathbf{v}_{\text{mode}}|^2 / \sigma_v^2}$$

- Anisotropy: mode $\Delta \mathbf{v}_{\text{mode}} \neq \mathbf{0}$ non-zero leads to a direction-dependent density which has cylindrical symmetry around the mode vector.

- ▶ After the initial velocity distribution has been propagated over a time interval, there is a spatial distribution of fragment density.
- ▶ The spatial distributions resulting from different initial velocity distributions may also be compared using the RMS technique.
- ▶ For each pair of initial velocity distributions, there is a pair of propagated distributions.

Simulation — general plan

- ▶ Unit simulation: create two velocity distributions which have high disparity, then compare the disparity of the resultant spatial distribution.
- ▶ Simulated cases
 - ▶ Total added energy: low, high, as reflected in the standard deviation σ_v .
 - ▶ Anisotropy: isotropic $\Delta v_{\text{mode}} = \mathbf{0}$, radial Δv_{mode} up and down, in-track Δv_{mode} fore and aft.
- ▶ For the purposes of this study, the comparison is limited
 - ▶ Single source orbit; only unperturbed density propagation at present.
 - ▶ For isotropic fragmentation, compare results with standard deviation of added velocity of varying values.
 - ▶ For fixed standard deviation (high), compare results with anisotropy none, along-track, anti-along-track, nadir, zenith.

Results: RMS differences isotropic with isotropic and different standard deviations

Name A	Name B	Velocity $s^3 km^{-3}$	Spatial 1 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$	Spatial 3 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$	Spatial 6 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$
I40	I80	5.17	4.12	3.66	2.10
I40	I120	6.09	5.39	4.33	2.18
I80	I120	1.34	1.86	0.99	1.46

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$$\sigma_v = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ at 1 hour}$$

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$$\sigma_v = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ at 1 hour}$$

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$\sigma_v = 120 \text{ms}^{-1}$ at 1 hour

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$$\sigma_v = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ at 3 hour}$$

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$$\sigma_v = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1} \text{ at 3 hour}$$

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$\sigma_v = 120 \text{ms}^{-1}$ at 3 hour

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$\sigma_v = 40 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at 6 hour

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$\sigma_v = 80 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ at 6 hour

Isotropic varying standard deviation σ_v

$\sigma_v = 120 \text{ ms}^{-1}$ at 6 hour

Results: RMS differences isotropic with isotropic and different standard deviations

- ▶ Note that the color map is on a logarithmic scale, so “obvious” differences in the distribution may be very close in RMS.
- ▶ These are only the $z = 0$ plane of a 3D density.
- ▶ Table again

Name A	Name B	Velocity s^3km^{-3}	Spatial 1 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 3 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}	Spatial 6 hr 10^{-11} km^{-3}
I40	I80	5.17	4.12	3.66	2.10
I40	I120	6.09	5.39	4.33	2.18
I80	I120	1.34	1.86	0.99	1.46

Results: RMS differences anisotropic with isotropic and different anisotropy

Name A	Name B	Velocity s^3km^{-3}	Spatial 1 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$	Spatial 3 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$	Spatial 6 hr $10^{-11} km^{-3}$
+X100	I80	1.87	2.61	1.37	2.07
-X100	I80	1.87	2.67	1.38	2.07
+Y100	I80	1.87	2.55	1.67	2.29
-Y100	I80	1.87	2.56	1.48	1.50
+Z100	I80	1.87	2.59	1.37	2.59
-Z100	I80	1.87	4.13	1.37	4.13
+X250	I80	3.14	4.28	2.30	3.68
+X500	I80	3.29	4.35	2.39	3.94
+X750	I80	3.29	4.24	2.35	4.17
+X1000	I80	2.88	3.89	2.28	3.30

Results discussion

- ▶ Isotropic, standard deviation is the most clearly inferable, pretty much uniform scaling factor.
- ▶ Anisotropic, less inferable.
- ▶ Unexplained: why does RMS drop at three hours and rise again at six hours for most of the initial distributions?
- ▶ Unexplained: -Z100 is quite a bit larger at one and six hours than anything else.

- ▶ Isotropic vs. isotropic, it is easier to distinguish low to high standard deviation than low to medium or medium to high.
- ▶ Anisotropic vs. isotropic, it is more difficult to distinguish distributions with modal velocity magnitude at 100 m/s, with the exception of -Z at one and six hours (but not three hours).
- ▶ Higher modal velocities (250 or more m/s) are more distinguishable (unclear why RMS flattens and then drops at 1 km/s).

Limitations and improvements

- ▶ Local characteristics are the key to distinguishing and inferring the modal velocity and even the standard deviation.
- ▶ RMS as the only metric is very limiting and even among global metrics may not be the best choice.
- ▶ A finer mesh might eliminate some of the variability.
- ▶ Noted odd trends: drop at 3 hours, -Z anisotropic.
- ▶ As a practical matter, sampling and blind spots (as well as source identification) makes the whole job significantly more challenging.

- ▶ Conference papers <https://zenodo.org/communities/eod>
- ▶ YouTube videos <https://tiny.cc/eodvideos>
- ▶ 2019 JAS paper, open access: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40295-018-00144-1>